

WOMEN, WORK, AND QUEST FOR BALANCE IN GLOBALIZATION ERA

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ABSTRACT

In current globalized society, women empowerment and work-life balance emerge as critical determinants of socio-economic progress and sustainable development. This paper delves into the intricate relationship between empowering women and achieving work-life balance amidst the rapid global integration of economies, cultures, and technologies. Globalization has expanded opportunities for women in education, employment, and entrepreneurship, yet it has also intensified challenges related to work-life balance due to increased competition and shifting labour market dynamics. The objective of this paper is to provide an overview of the impact of globalization on women's empowerment and challenges facing by women employees of India in maintaining a balance between her personal and professional life. This study is based on secondary data. It suggested that empowerment initiatives, such as flexible working arrangements, equitable parental leave policies, and supportive workplace environments, enable women to harmonize their professional and personal responsibilities. It concluded that achieving this balance enhances women's productivity, job satisfaction, and career progression, thereby contributing to organizational success and economic growth. Moreover, balanced work-life dynamics lead to improved mental and physical health, stronger family bonds, and more active community engagement. The interplay of these elements is essential for fostering a more equitable, productive, and resilient society.

KEYWORDS: Globalization, Women's Empowerment, Work-Life Balance, Sustainable Development

INTRODUCTION

In 1991, at the time of the Narsimha Rao government a new economic policy was adopted. The aim of this policy was to improve the economic condition of the country. Through liberalization, privatization and globalization policy Indian government opened the doors of the country for foreign investment. This policy brought a lot of changes in the economic and social system of the country. With the advent of this policy, working culture of the country has been changed. Globalization has provided a lot of positives and negatives to Indian society. It impacted the whole social structure of the country whether it is roles, statuses, groups, organizations, social institutions, social networks, etc. It has changed the way of life of every member of society. The women's group is also one of them. People in society, especially women, now have more work options than before. Globalization dismantled the way women were traditionally treated and aided them in achieving equality in society. It increased their quality of life, made them more confident and self-reliant, reduced the gender gap, and allowed them to prove themselves in this male dominating society.

Along with the dazzling picture of globalization, there is a dark side too. Globalization brought industrialization and it did the work of snatching jobs of many people. It ruined many traditional industries such as handloom and food processing, where women previously

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worked in significant numbers. On one side, it introduced women to the workplace, provided them an opportunity to work at a common platform, given the right to live life on their own terms and conditions. Another side, it puts them under enormous pressure. Many reports show that working women are more prone to mental illness. According to NHMS 2015-16, “neurosis and stress-related disorders affected 3.5% of the population and was reported to be higher among females (nearly twice as much as males).” Globalization has made the economy volatile and competitive. It has created a scenario of fierce competition, job insecurity, ambitious goals, tough deadlines, heavy workload, and dreadful performance appraisals. All these are adding stress to people’s life. Finding the ideal balance between one's personal and professional lives is getting increasingly difficult.

WORK-LIFE BALANCE FOR WOMEN

Work-Life Balance for a woman refers to maintain a stable balance between her professional, personal, and family life. It means balancing responsibilities at workplace and home in order to preserve overall well-being and contentment in both areas of life.

Kalliath and Brough proposed a definition of the WLB that is “Work–life balance is the individual perception that work and nonwork activities are compatible and promote growth in accordance with an individual’s current life priorities.” Work-life balance is a state in which an individual tries to strike a balance between career, family, and other areas of their lives at a particular time. Work-life balance is not about giving equal time to professional, personal, and social life but it’s the ability to meet personal, professional, and social responsibilities satisfactorily.

STATISTICS RELATED TO WORKING WOMEN IN INDIA

According to Census 2011, India’s population was 121.1 Crore with 48.5% female population. Women's labor force participation is 25.51%, while men's is 53.26%. As per the latest available Annual PLFS Reports, the estimated Worker Population Ratio (WPR) and Labour Force Participation Rate (LFPR) on usual status for females of age 15 years and above during the years 2017-18 to 2022-23 are as follows:

Table:1 Worker Population Ratio and Labour Force Participation Rate of Females (15 years and above) from Year 2017 to 2023 (in %) on Usual Status

Years	WPR (in %)	LFPR (in %)
2017-18	22.0	23.3
2018-19	23.3	24.5
2019-20	28.7	30.0
2020-21	31.4	32.5
2021-22	31.7	32.8
2022-23	35.9	37.0

Source: PLFS, MoSPI

Figure:1 Trends in Worker Population Ratio and Labour Force Participation Rate of Females (15 years and above) from Year 2017 to 2023 (in %) on Usual Status

The data indicates that the women's participation in labour force and the workforce has significantly increased over the years. During 2022-23, the women participation in labour force has notable increased to 37.0%.

As per PLFS 2021-22, about 33.6% of women wanted to continue their studies, while 44.5% cited childcare/personal commitments in homemaking as reasons for not participating in the labour force.

According to National Family Health Survey-5, Women who engaged in paid work in India is 25.4 % only.

India Today reported, "female labour participation in India is declining. It reported that less than 20% of India's women work at paid jobs and female workforce participation has been declining in the country." There are lots of reasons for this declining participation such as dual responsibilities, unsafe workplaces, gender biases, odd working hours, lack of social support, etc.

According to McKinsey Global Institute's report, the power of parity: Advancing women's equality in Asia-Pacific (2018), the contribution of women to India's GDP is 18 percent, one of the lowest proportions in the world, reflecting the fact that only 25 percent of India's labour force is female. More than 70 percent of the potential GDP opportunity comes from increasing women's participation in the labour force by 10 percentage points.

WOMEN QUEST FOR BALANCE IN INDIA

Globalization provided tremendous opportunities to Indian women but it remained to fail to absolve them from social obligations. Working women frequently face discrimination based on their gender, unequal compensation, and little prospects for career growth. Furthermore, striking a balance between job and family obligations is extremely difficult, particularly in light of societal expectations and insufficient parental leave regulations. Many times, they have to leave the job. A study conducted by The Udaiti Foundation and Center for Economic Data & Analysis (CEDA) reported, "34% of women in India exit firms over work-life balance while only 4% of men do so."

A major concern for working women in India is finding a work-life balance, which is impacted by a variety of organizational, personal, and sociocultural issues such as:

TRADITIONAL GENDER ROLES

It is the irony of Indian society, even today women are assumed to take care of the house only. Our society has been unable to free them from the trap of traditional gender roles. As per United Nations Organization report namely, Gender Equality: Why it matters,

“International commitments to advance gender equality have brought about improvements in some areas: child marriage and female genital mutilation (FGM) have declined in recent years, and women’s representation in the political arena is higher than ever before. But the promise of a world in which every woman and girl enjoys full gender equality, and where all legal, social, and economic barriers to their empowerment have been removed, remains unfulfilled.” Data from the International Labour Organisation (ILO) states that the employability gender gap in India is 50.9%, with only 19.2% of women in the labour force compared to 70.1% of men.

DUAL RESPONSIBILITIES

Now a days, it is expected from the woman that she should be employed and have perfect in house making. Before going to office and after reaching at home she has to accomplish all household tasks. She often faces the dual burden. Even in households where both partners work, women typically take on a larger share of domestic responsibilities. As per government estimates, women across different age groups spend exponentially more hours per day doing unpaid work like household chores or caregiving activities, than their male counterparts. An average Indian woman aged between 15 and 29 spends around 5.5 hours doing unpaid labor in a day whereas a man spends about 50 minutes on unpaid tasks. The value of unpaid labor of women across rural and urban areas in India was estimated to be over 22 trillion Indian rupees in 2019.

HIGH PERFORMANCE EXPECTATIONS

In this globalization era, workplaces become more competitive and work demanding. Employers’ expectations are growing day by day. With increased competition and performance metrics, women may feel pressured to consistently outperform to prove their capabilities, which can lead to stress and burnout. Often, women take career breaks for childbirth and caregiving, which hinders their career progression and result in loss of seniority or skills. Balancing work and home life leaves little time for networking or seeking mentorship, which are crucial for career advancement. Even Indian society do not permit working women to engage in informal networking activities, which are crucial for career advancement, especially if these activities occur outside of regular working hours.

PROFESSIONAL CHALLENGES

In India, globalization has helped in educating women and sending them to jobs, but it is yet to free them from familial responsibilities. Many factors such as urbanization, industrialization, higher levels of education, rights awareness, media impact, etc. have contributed to change the aspirations of female and their status in society. Now, they are more ambitious and concerned about career development. They aim for high-level jobs and these jobs demand long and irregular working hours. They have to commute to distant places to fulfil organizational responsibilities. Many times, they do not get support from family members which leads them towards conflict.

GLOBAL MOBILITY AND RELOCATION

Globalization offered global career opportunities to women. To avail these opportunities, they often need to relocate. Many times, this can be challenging due to family commitments, children's education, and the difficulty of adapting to new cultural environments. Relocating to a new country or city can disrupt existing support systems, such as extended family and friends, which are crucial for managing domestic responsibilities.

SUPPORT SYSTEM

In India, access to affordable and reliable childcare and elder care services are critical for working women. In many places, such infrastructure is either inadequate or prohibitively expensive. Although there are laws for maternity leave, not all organizations comply fully, and paternity leave is often minimal or nonexistent, placing the burden primarily on women. Many organizations lack policies that support work-life balance, such as on-site childcare, eldercare assistance, or wellness programs.

TECHNOLOGICAL ADVANCEMENTS AND CONNECTIVITY

The proliferation of digital technology has been extended beyond traditional office hours. Now employees have to remain available on calls even after official working hours. It blurs the boundaries between work and personal life. It leads to a situation where work encroaches on personal time and space, making it harder to switch off and recharge.

HEALTH AND WELL-BEING

Women work around the clock to compete at the workplace and to meet the social demands of a patriarchal society. This leads them towards various physical, social, and psychological issues such as body aches, role conflict, job pressure, mental exhaustion, stress, anxiety, frustration, etc. Resultant, it adds discomfort in their life.

SUGGESTIONS TO HARMONIZE PERSONAL AND PROFESSIONAL LIFE

Dismantling the imbalance between work and life, especially in the context of women's empowerment, requires a multi-faceted approach involving policy changes, organizational practices, and cultural shifts. The following suggestions can be used to harmonize personal and professional responsibilities:

- 1. Policy Interventions:** Governments and organizations should promote policies related to parental leave, flexible working arrangements, and gender equality. It would be beneficial for working women to obtain balance in their life.
- 2. Cultural Change:** There is a need to make changes in the traditional gender roles. People should value and support women in their career alongside their personal lives. This includes promoting shared domestic responsibilities between men and women.
- 3. Support Networks:** Establishing robust support systems can aid women in overcoming the difficulties of juggling work and life. Both formal (such as professional mentoring programs) and informal (such as community support groups), could be started. It will help women in navigating the challenges of balancing work and life.
- 4. Personal Boundaries:** Women can benefit from setting clear boundaries between work and personal time, prioritizing self-care, and seeking professional help when needed to manage stress and maintain mental health.
- 5. Health and Well-being Programs:** Government and organizations should offer wellness programs, mental health support, and self-care resources for women to manage stress and maintain their health.
- 6. Organizational Changes:** Government should encourage employers to adopt family-friendly policies, provide on-site childcare, and create a culture that values work-life balance.

7. **Support for Unpaid Care Work:** There is a need to recognise and value unpaid care work performed by women and promote shared responsibilities within households. Encourage men's involvement in caregiving and domestic responsibilities will be helpful in dismantling the imbalance between work and life.
8. **Equal Pay and Workplace Policies:** Government should enforce equal pay for equal work policies, promotes gender diversity in leadership positions, and implements workplace policies that support work-life balance and safe working environment free from harassment and discrimination.

By implementing these measures, government and organizations can create an environment that supports the well-being of all employees especially women, leading to increased job satisfaction, productivity, and overall organizational success and economic growth.

CONCLUSION

In nutshell, it can be said that globalization played an important role in the empowerment of Indian women. It provided a lot of opportunities to females. Also, it confers unique challenges for them in achieving work-life balance. Addressing these challenges requires a comprehensive approach that includes policy changes, cultural shifts, and individual strategies. By fostering an environment that supports women's multifaceted roles, societies can ensure that the benefits of globalization are equitably shared.

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